

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NDARUHUTSE****FIRST NAME: ALFRED****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What is the point of referencing sources being utilized during research?

- Adds to the credibility of the author¹**
- Increases readability of text
- Highlights research method
- Gets approval of participants involved

2. What is the best way to avoid Plagiarism in research?

- Citation
- Paraphrasing
- Changing grammar and voices
- All of the above²**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Washington, D.C. Euclid University Press, 2024), 45.

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 67.

3. What is the major difference between UK and US English?

- Grammar and punctuation³**
- Names for every transportation
- Syntax
- Morphology

4. What distinguishes primary sources from secondary sources?

- Raw data⁴**
- Advancing the already available research
- Refining of prior studies
- Critiquing primary data

5. Citing a source is essential; which of the following are the key requirements needed for citing a journal article?

- Author's name, journal name, DOI
- Author, date of publication, abstract, DOI
- Date of publication, name of journal, DOI, abstract
- Name of author, journal, publication date, DOI/URL, title of article⁵**

6. Which framework for the dissertation is described as an overarching framework by Dr. James?

- Research bias
- Prospectus

³ European Commission, *English Style Guide*, 8th ed. (Brussels: European Union, 2021), 10.

⁴ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 102.

⁵ European Commission, *English Style Guide*, 8th ed., 21.

- Research design**⁶
 - Literature review
7. What aspects in the field of diplomacy and international relations are targeted by Luxardo?
- Focus on cultural aspects
 - Focus on media depiction
 - Focus on economic patterns**⁷
 - Focus on qualitative aspects
8. Which aspects are focused in the dissertation prospectus?
- Ruling out personal bias
 - Quantitative and qualitative analysis
 - Ruling out international bias
 - Research questions and objectives**⁸
9. What shortcoming is identified in Farahat's work?
- Improper evaluation of recent media debates
 - No usage of expansive bibliography
 - Lack of integration of political factors with other disciplinary questions
 - Lack of support to back up the claims made**⁹
10. The European Commission has certain guidelines regarding use of punctuation; which among the below statements describes their guidelines on use of semicolons?

⁶ John Creswell, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 4th ed. (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2023), 33.

⁷ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 58.

⁸ Creswell, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 4th ed., 40.

⁹ Creswell, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 4th ed., 82.

- A semicolon is used to join independent clauses when a conjunction is present.
- A semicolon is used to join independent clauses when a conjunction is not present.
- Are used to join two independent clauses when a conjunction is not needed.**¹⁰
- They are only usable in professional circumstances.

¹⁰ European Commission, *English Style Guide*, 8th ed., 18.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 5th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024.

Creswell, John. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. 4th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2023.

European Commission. *English Style Guide*. 8th ed. Brussels: European Union, 2021.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.